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**STRATEGIES FOR INNOVATIVE AND SUSTAINABLE FUNDING OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE
EDUCATION IN A CHALLENGED ECONOMY**

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents strategies for innovative and sustainable funding of agricultural science education in a challenged economy in a 9 point agenda as innovative strategies to enhance the funding of tertiary education in Nigeria, these are: Alternative Learning Modes, Advocacy and policy changes, Personal Financial Planning, Alumni and Philanthropic Support, Explore International Opportunities, Entrepreneurial and Freelance Work, Institutional Partnerships, Community based Strategies and Government and Institutional Supports. Combining these strategies can make tertiary education more accessible and affordable to all even in a challenged economy, like we are experiencing and having in Nigeria.

Keywords: Strategies, Innovative and Sustainable Funding, Challenged Economy

INTRODUCTION

Strategies may be defined as carefully designed methods to be used to achieve specific goals or solve particular problems. It involves analyzing the situation, setting objectives to be pursued and determining the best course of actions to be taken in order to achieve the desirable set objectives as outcomes. Often times, good strategies require resource allocation, consideration of possible challenges along the process of executing the strategies and adapting to dynamic and changing situations in the process of carrying out the strategies. Therefore, strategies in simple term may be defined as the “how to” plans for reaching a particular goal.

Innovation is the process of creating, developing and executing new ideas, methods, products or services that can add value or improve the existing system; in this case, the system of funding tertiary education in Nigeria. The need for innovation is mostly borne out of dissatisfaction with the status quo, thus; innovation involves introducing something novel and new on what already exists in order to solve problems, meet needs or enhance efficiency and effectiveness of a particular system. Usually, innovation drives progress and fosters growth in various fields either in form of product, process, social or business model innovations.

The status quo of funding tertiary education in Nigeria is grossly inadequate, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) agreement at its 38th General Conference in Paris on 4/11/2015 recommended 15% to 20% of annual budget or 4% to 6% of Gross Domestic Product to fund education in any country of member states; however, in Nigeria (which is a UNESCO member state) only 1.5 trillion naira which represents 7.9% in 2024, 1.08 trillion naira which represents 8.8% in 2023 and in 2022, it was 1.18 trillion naira, that is 7.2% of the annual budget (Premium Times Nig.) was allocated to education, thus; the need for devising additional innovative sources of funding tertiary education. Also, UNESCO Education 2030 Framework For Action (FFA) (2024) provides guidance for member countries for the implementation of Education 2030 agenda which aims to mobilize all stakeholders in education around the ambitious education goals and targets, and proposes ways of implementing, coordinating, financing and reviewing the 2030 education agenda – globally, regionally and nationally – to guarantee equal educational opportunity for all. The consistent underfunding of education in Nigeria poses significant challenges, including low quality education, high dropout rates and a substantial number of out of school children. To ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all, there is urgent need for innovation in funding education in Nigeria not only at the tertiary level but across all levels of education and in a sustainable fashion.

Sustainable funding implies ability to meet current needs without compromising the resources for meeting future generations' needs. Sustainability refers to maintaining balance and ensuring long term health and stability of key systems namely: social, environmental and economic systems. Sustainability means continuity without halting to ensure a viable future. The social aspect of sustainability has to do with equity, well being, and access for all individuals, fostering inclusive and resilient communities like having access to education and health care. The economic aspect has to do with fair trade, financial stability to support long term economic growth without causing any harm to social or environmental systems; while the environmental aspect has to do with protecting the ecosystem from degradation through responsible use of natural resources (conservation efforts, use renewable energy). Example of sustainable funding practices include scouting for new and practicable ways of funding agricultural science education in tertiary institutions in addition to the currently existing ways to maintain continuous financing while promoting sustainable smart agriculture and responsible consumption patterns, making prudent use of allocated and generated funds for the purpose it was meant. Funding tertiary education in a challenged economy requires innovative strategies and careful financial planning.

Funding is the provision of resources like money to support any activity or project by an individual or organizations. Funding is essential for enabling ventures such as education pursuits, research projects, business or infrastructural development. Funding may be obtained from personal, public, private, crowd, loans or equity sources. Funding is critical for achieving goals and sustaining operations across various sectors including agricultural science education in tertiary institutions.

According to Amadi and Blessing (2016), agricultural education is a vocational subject taught at all levels of education starting from primary to tertiary level of education; while Makusdi (2016) defined agricultural education as education that leads to practical skills acquisition, scientific knowledge and attitudes leading to a specific vocation in the society like crop production, animal husbandry, horticulture *et cetera*. Agricultural education helps learners to be exposed to real life situations and experiences through demonstrations, field trips, excursions, laboratories (field & indoor) and classroom lectures. Agricultural education is therefore a process of training learners in process of agricultural productivity as well as techniques for teaching agriculture (Ali, *et. al.* (2020)). Agricultural science education (ASE) in this study; is a 4 year

vocational education course offered in the University. It involves the acquisition of skills, knowledge and attitudes required to enter into a job or career in agriculture; and its recipients have the added advantage of being trained and prepared to become agricultural science educators (agricultural science teachers) at the basic school, secondary school or colleges on graduation. It's a course that is associated with a lot of practical in the indoor laboratory and on the field (outdoor laboratory) after the theory sessions in the classroom. Many facilities required for training the students are in short supply, forcing the need for this write up – innovative and sustainable funding of ASE to augment the dearth of facilities in a challenged economy.

A challenged economy refers to an economic system that is experiencing significant difficulties or obstacles hindering its growth, stability or overall performance. These challenges can arise from internal or external factors and often result in negative impacts on businesses, households and governments. A challenged economy is characterized by high unemployment (large part of the population will be without jobs – pseudo employment, under employment or none employment), low economic growth (low or stagnant increase in production of goods and services-GDP), unstable prices for goods and services (inflation or deflation), declining investments in businesses, infrastructure and innovation, political instability, rising poverty levels (increased financial struggles for households and high social inequality) and currency instability – fluctuations of currency impacting imports, exports and savings; consequently investments. All these characteristics are vividly witnessed in Nigeria's economy.

A country's economy may be challenged due to many reasons, some of these include: global economic downturns, corruption, political instability, poor fiscal and monetary policies, natural disasters or pandemics and high levels of debts or fiscal deficits. The impacts of a challenged economy include: reduced living standards, limited access to resources and increased reliance on external aids or loans. The ways out of a challenged economy may include any of the following: reforms, strategic interventions and investments in education, infrastructure and industry. This is the main reason why this conference is apt and timely, calling for reforms in the ways tertiary institutions are being funded and making a clarion call on all stakeholders to invest more than ever before in education. Some of the strategies that may be used to fund tertiary education are presented below, this list is not exhaustive in any way as there can be many more than those presented here. In this paper, they are called the 9 point innovative strategies.

THE 9 POINT INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES

This paper presents a 9 point agenda as innovative strategies, which if implemented and coordinated very well can provide sustainable funding for tertiary education in a challenged economy including Agricultural Science Education. They are:

1. Alternative Learning Modes
2. Advocacy and policy changes
3. Personal Financial Planning
4. Alumni and Philanthropic Support
5. Explore International Opportunities
6. Entrepreneurial and Freelance Work
7. Institutional Partnerships
8. Community Based Strategies
9. Government and Institutional Supports

ALTERNATIVE LEARNING MODES

This strategy involves majorly online education mode which is cheaper and affordable than the traditional schools; also, students can focus on shorter targeted programs that offer job-ready skills at lower costs (this is also referred to as micro-credentials or certificates). The main advantage of this strategy is the short gestation period to graduation and completion of the course; skills acquired are easily marketable making the graduates to be hired soon after completion of their schooling. Skills in single enterprise can be organized and offered online as courses to be certificated example; fattening of cattle, production of rabbits, poultry, grafting/budding and production of seedlings of permanent crops, production of horticultural crops (vegetables or flowers) *et cetera*. All skill areas in agriculture can be designed as short modular courses and offered online to interested recipients on a short term basis; which on completion of such skill training can start using the skills acquired to earn incomes and contribute to the economy by being productive using their newly learned skills. Many students can be skilled by this approach at the least cost possible in a challenged economy.

ADVOCACY AND POLICY CHANGES

This strategy is very critical for education policy formulation especially in a situation where the stakeholders are politically informed. It involves lobbying for education reforms that will prioritize access and affordability to quality education through political representatives from the various constituencies in the country. Also, with adequate political awareness and information, the electorates (citizens) can advocate for tax incentives for individuals or organizations that contribute to education funds in form of tax holidays benefits for donors.

PERSONAL FINANCIAL PLANNING

This strategy involves personal decision and discipline to commit to savings plans known as education savings account, this may be started early in small amounts as a student plans to further their education after the secondary schools. Another dimension to personal financial planning is to cut costs to reduce living and education expenses; students must decide to stay in low cost accommodation, buy and use used textbooks and use public transport instead of private transportation mode. All these costs cutting actions will provide allowances for funding their education with more convenience than when and if such decisions and sacrifices were not made.

ALUMNI AND PHILANTHROPIC SUPPORT

This strategy involves old students association of a specific school to fund, mentor and sponsor the education of current students in such institutions in form of award to indigent students, scholarship for best overall performance and so on as reported by Banka and Bua, (2015). Also, charity organizations focused on education at no profit can be encouraged to fund education as part of corporate social responsibility (CSR)

EXPLORE INTERNATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES

This strategy involves leveraging exchange programs at little or no cost to the students that allow them studying abroad (overseas) through the Federal Ministry of Education. Qualified applicants and prospective students should apply for

international scholarships, fellowships and so on, through this strategy; education of many students will be funded at no personal costs.

ENTREPRENEURIAL AND FREELANCE WORK

This strategy requires students to engage in side businesses like tutoring to generate income to support their schooling. Also, students can combine study with few hours work outside study schedules for example engaging in night/day shift service at a café or fuel service stations to earn money to augment and support their education. Students can go for paid farm jobs “*barema*” at weekends (Saturdays or Sundays) when schools are not in session to earn income (funds) to support funding of their education for example buy books or pay for other education bills as the need may arise.

INSTITUTIONAL PARTNERSHIPS

Here two approaches can be possible and used as strategies to fund education as follow:

a. Work/study programs

Under this approach, the institution collaborates with local businesses to provide part-time jobs for students to assist the students in training to fund their education.

b. Corporate sponsorship

Here institutions partner with companies to fund students’ education in exchange for employment agreement after graduation when students complete their training.

Either way, if used efficiently these approaches may be very useful and effective in assisting students to fund their education in a challenged economy like we have in Nigeria.

COMMUNITY BASED STRATEGIES

In this strategy, students seek and solicit education financial support from members of their community such as friends, family members and relatives, and the rich/wealthy in the society. There can also be a kind of arrangement by members within the society whereby resources will be pooled together to fund student’s education in exchange for future community service or a commitment to the community later in life by the student after graduation.

GOVERNMENT AND INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORTS

The government and private organizations through tertiary institutions can provide scholarships based on merits, give grants based on needs or subsidize education by reducing the costs for education essential services like reduce tuition fees, costs of textbooks, cost of accommodation and so on. The government can also introduce and implement income-contingent loans like Student’s Loan Scheme which can be repaid based on graduate’s income level to ease repayment pressure after securing paid job (employment) after graduation at 2% to 4% interest rates. Currently in Nigeria, the Nigerian Education Loan Fund (NELFUND) just updated its disbursement as at January, 2025, this is commendable, it should be publicized more for students to apply and benefit from the scheme. The State Governments in Nigeria can also embark on similar schemes to assist students to fund education in their various states.

CONCLUSION

There is no one way to fund education or solve any problem but combining these strategies can make tertiary education to be well funded, become more robust in its operations, accessible and affordable to all even in a challenged economy like we are experiencing in Nigeria.

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